

The Analysis of Legal Regulations for Establishing and Operating Reuse Centers or Points

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Abstract: The circular economy and sustainability are concepts that are mutually interconnected and have been the subject of debate and research. The circular economy primarily focuses on the sustainable use of resources. Reuse centers and reuse points are concrete examples of implementing the reuse principle, which contributes to a more efficient use of resources and a reduction of the negative impact on the environment. Establishing and running a reuse center or reuse point has several positive impacts (economic, environmental, and social), but there are also legal aspects that need to be considered when deciding on the form and system of their operation. The aim of this paper is to identify the legal norms (laws and decrees) as well as other legal regulations that are applicable to the topic of establishing re-use centers/re-use points. This includes a comparative analysis of the current forms of establishing these operations to summarize the advantages, disadvantages, and risks associated with each form. Another objective is to synthesize these legal regulations into basic clusters according to their relevance to different aspects of the operation of re-use centers/reuse – points.

Keywords: reuse centers; reuse points; circular economy; sustainability; legal regulations; municipalities

JEL Classification: O56, K22, H44

1. Introduction

Reuse centers and reuse points are facilities or places that focus on promoting the reuse and recycling of items. These centers help reduce waste and promote sustainability by extending the lifetime of things and minimizing the consumption of new raw materials. Sustainability encompasses economic, social, and environmental dimensions, seeking to balance the needs of people and the preservation of resources. As stated by Nilashi et al. (2019), nowadays sustainability is recognized as one of the most important paradigms of development and is included in the international and national strategies of almost all organizations. The schemes used by organizations to manage sustainability efforts are evaluated by Demastus and Landrum (2023) in their research. According to Hicks and Nergard (2023), the sustainability of a particular place is also influenced by the physical and social infrastructure of the environment. Sustainability is linked to the circular economy as they share common goals of efficient use of resources, minimizing waste, and avoiding or reducing negative environmental impacts. The circular economy is considered an alternative

to the existing economic activity models and has become one of the newest ways to address environmental sustainability (Pichlak, 2018; Bareiro-Gen & Lozano, 2023). The principles of adoption or barriers to the implementation and development of the circular economy are therefore the subject of research, which is addressed, for example, by Garfström and Aasma (2021), Patwa et al. (2021), or Sorensen et al. (2020).

Reuse centers, or reuse points, play an important role in the circular economy. The concept of reuse is defined by the EU Directive 2018/851/EU (2018) as an activity in which products or components that do not constitute waste are reused for the same purpose for which they were created. As Milios (2018) states, reuse brings environmental, social, and economic benefits. The potential and environmental benefits of reusing end-of-life products are reported, for example, by Milios and Dalhammar (2020) or Maier et al. (2020). Social and societal benefits are mentioned by Gorissen et al. (2014). Economic aspects of reuse centers and reuse points are examined by, e.g., Zacho et al. (2018) or Zajko and Hojnik (2014).

In the Czech Republic, establishing a reuse center or reuse point should be done with respect to local legislation, the market, and the needs of the community. A reuse center is usually a larger facility through which other services can be offered, including recycling and waste education activities. A reuse point is a designated place where items that can still be used are deposited. Sustainability in the context of reuse centers and reuse points is a key element that should reflect their entire operation. Establishers should familiarize themselves in detail with the relevant legislation and regulatory requirements relating to the operation and responsibility for a reuse center or reuse point. Non-legal aspects, such as communication and cooperation with local authorities and stakeholders or securing funding for its operation, also play an important role in the establishment of a reuse center or reuse point.

A legal entity, a natural person doing business, or a state or local government body can become the founders of reuse centers or reuse points. For the purposes of this article, the establisher is categorized into private entities, i.e., natural persons (self-employed persons), legal persons that are established directly by natural persons, and state or local government bodies. Given the scope of the legal environment of the area, this paper focuses on the analysis of the legal regulations related to the moment of selecting the legal form for establishing a reuse center or reuse point and subsequently on defining the legal regulations related to their operation. The authors see the importance of this topic since the legal regulations relating to this topic are fragmented within the legal system, and therefore the relevant provisions of law have to be extracted and grouped together according to the problem area addressed.

The aim of this paper is to identify the legal norms (laws and decrees) as well as other legal regulations that are applicable to the topic of establishing re-use centerst/re-use points. This includes a comparative analysis of the current forms of establishing these operations to summarize the advantages, disadvantages, and risks associated with each form. Another objective is to synthesize these legal regulations into basic clusters according to their relevance to different aspects of the operation of re-use centers/reuse – points.

2. Methodology

Several complementary scientific methods will be used to meet the set objectives. To elaborate on an analysis of the legal regulations for establishing and operating a reuse center or reuse point, we will use both literal and extensional methods of interpretation of the law. In particular, the latter will be applied to the relevant legal regulations at the level of acts and decrees. Furthermore, the scientific method of desk research, the method of analyzing legal regulations and decrees, and the method of data comparison will be used. Another method that will be employed is the method of clustering legal regulations into individual groups, according to which a methodology for establishing and operating a reuse center or reuse point will be drawn up.

To achieve the set objective, the following research questions have been formulated:

1. What legal norms govern the establishment of re-use centers/re-use points, and what forms are currently available under these legal norms? What are the advantages, disadvantages, and risks associated with each legal form?
2. Is it crucial for establishing a reuse center or reuse point which entity (private or public) establishes the reuse center or reuse point?
3. What legal norms identify the issues of operating a reuse center or reuse point, or more precisely, what basic clusters can be defined for these legal norms?

All legal regulations referred to herein are stated as subsequently amended.

3. Results

3.1. The Analysis of the Legal Forms of Establishing a Reuse Center, a Reuse Point, and the Identification of Legal Regulations

Reuse centers or reuse points can be operated by natural persons (in the Czech Republic referred to as self-employed persons), by trade corporations acting in legal relations as private entities, or by local governments through legal persons or trade corporations that are defined and regulated for this activity in the Czech legal system. The legal system of the Czech Republic defines several legal persons and trade corporations that are used in practice for establishing reuse centers and reuse points. Selecting the legal form for a reuse center or reuse point depends on several factors, including the objective of the organization, its structure, funding, and legal obligations. The entity establishing the reuse center or reuse point also represents an important factor in the establishment process. The process of establishment itself, i.e., the choice of the most appropriate legal form, subsequently influences the operation in terms of the need to comply with the obligations that are regulated by the relevant legal norms relating to the operation.

First of all, the establisher should define factors that will enable them to select the most appropriate legal form for operating the reuse center or reuse point:

1. Defining the objectives: The objectives of a reuse center or reuse point should be defined by the establisher before the establishment process. Whether the founder's priority and

primary objective are to achieve social or environmental gains, or whether the established reuse center or reuse point should have a commercial aspect, should be defined.

2. Profitability of the reuse center or reuse point: This is an entirely fundamental question when selecting the legal form of the reuse center or reuse point. At the very beginning of the establishment, it should be decided whether the reuse center or reuse point is to be a profit-making organization or a non-profit organization. This decision subsequently affects the way the operation is financed and the tax obligations.
3. Financial aspects: financial aspects, including available funding sources, must be considered for running a reuse center or reuse point. Non-profit organizations can secure their funding through subsidy programs or grants, while commercial entities most often rely on their revenues or on financial support from other private entities. Reuse centers and reuse points can also be funded through public fundraising. A public fundraising campaign is not directly a legal person. Only legal persons, not individual citizens, are entitled to organize public fundraising (Act No. 117/2001 Sb.).
4. Stakeholders' interests: the selected legal form of the reuse center or reuse point should respect the following interests: These are the interests of the local communities (creating job opportunities, the possibility of being involved in the recycling and reuse process, benefits for the local economy), the interests of employees (retraining opportunities, support of unemployment, support of weak social groups), the interests of business partners (maintaining stable business relations, transparent communication, establishing cooperation), and the interests of investors or financing organizations (securing return on investment, long-term sustainability of projects, transparent financial management).
5. Legal liability and risks: To select the right legal form of reuse center or reuse point, personal liability, tax burden, and risks associated with the legal form in question must be taken into account.
6. Sustainable business plan: the selected legal form should allow for future development and adaptation to changes, both market and legal. Therefore, strategies and long-term plans for the operation of them must be defined prior to establishing the reuse center or reuse point.

Depending on their objectives, structure, and needs, reuse centers and reuse points can take different legal forms in the Czech Republic. However, the legal status of the establisher means a certain limitation, which must also be considered in this context. There is no legal limitation in terms of the private entity as the establisher. In the case of the establisher being a state authority or a local government authority, the limitation is directly defined by the legal regulations.

The establishment of a facility by a private entity

A private entity can establish and operate a reuse center or reuse point as a business entity that is intended to make a profit, not only through the legal forms of trade corporations but also through conducting business activities using a trade license. When selecting the legal form (Table 1) for establishing a reuse center or reuse point, it is

important to understand that there is a certain risk of limited access to external financing. An equally important aspect is that within these legal forms, a social or environmental focus may be lacking. Considering that legal forms such as corporations or sole proprietorships are established to generate profit, the financing of the operation of the reuse center or reuse point is also secured to some extent.

Table 1. The comparison of legal forms for establishing a reuse business when the business entity is a profit-making private entity (Part 1)

Form	Limited liability company	Joint-stock company	Cooperative	Licensed trade	General commercial partnership
Characteristics	Limited liability company. The founders hold shares in the profits and have limited liability. The executive director bears personal liability for the company's debts in the given circumstance, involving the encumbrance of their personal assets. Legal provisions govern the particulars of such instances	A joint stock company is a form of business entity that issues its own shares. It is suitable for larger projects and makes it possible to raise capital from shareholders. Shareholders have an ownership interest in the business corporation.	It is only an option when the cooperation and participation of individual members are emphasized. To operate a reuse center or reuse point, this legal form of operating a social cooperative should be chosen.	Operated on one's own responsibility. Suitable for smaller reuse centers and reuse points. Obtaining a trade license is required, the categorization of which will be based on the type of activity carried out. Carried out by a natural person as a self-employed person.	Characterized by a democratic management style. Individual members decide on business matters.
Legal regulations	Section 132 et seq. of Act No. 90/2012 Sb., on Business Corporations and Cooperatives	Section 243 et seq. of Act No. 90/2012 Sb., on Business Corporations and Cooperatives	Section 552 et seq. of Act No. 90/2012 Sb., on Business Corporations and Cooperatives	Section 45 et seq. of Act No. 455/1991 Sb., the Trade Licensing Act	Section 95 et seq. of Act No. 90/2012 Coll., on Business Corporations and Cooperatives
Advantages	Low share capital of 1 CZK.	High capital stock.	Cooperative members actively participate in the decision-making process. Each member has the right to participate in strategic operational issues.	Simple, quick, and time- and money-saving establishment of a licensed trade.	It does not create share capital.

Table 1. The comparison of legal forms for establishing a reuse business when the business entity is a profit-making private entity (Part 2)

Form	Limited liability company	Joint-stock company	Cooperative	Licensed trade	General commercial partnership
Disadvantages	The executive director bears personal liability for the company's debts in the given circumstance, involving the encumbrance of their personal assets. Legal provisions govern the particulars of such instances. There exists a restricted option for discontinuing share participation in the company.	Shareholders' equity participation is intended only for large projects; in the authors' opinion, this is not a suitable form for reuse centers or reuse points.	Less flexible than a limited liability company or joint stock company, which reduces the speed of response to market changes and new opportunities.	Unlimited liability for the debts of the reuse center or reuse point, i.e., by the natural person's entire property.	Unlimited liability, dependence on members who bring their own personal know-how to the company.
Risks	Lack of social orientation, lack of social or environmental orientation.	Open ownership leads to reduced control by founders and companies.	All members of the cooperative share responsibility for losses.	Professional qualifications or education are required for some activities performed at the reuse center or reuse point.	Persons are jointly and severally liable for debts with all their property.

Act No. 90/2012 Sb., the Business Corporations Act, regulates another type of business corporation under Section 118. This is a limited partnership, which can be defined as a company combining elements of a limited liability company and a general commercial partnership. According to the authors, this partnership can be used for operating a reuse center or reuse point, but its internal structure appears to be complicated for operation.

A private entity can establish and operate a reuse center or reuse point with an emphasis on social and environmental aspects. To fulfill these aspects, the legal form of non-profit organizations is chosen (Table 2). Using this legal form, reuse centers and reuse points most often provide employment opportunities for people who may have limited access to the labor

market, offer education and training programs, or carry out educational activities by informing the public about the importance of sustainability and reducing negative environmental impacts. Thus, the legal form of non-profit organizations is not focused on generating profit for the reuse center or reuse point.

Table 2. The comparison of legal forms for establishing a reuse business in the legal form of non-profit organization – a private entity

Form	Association	Endowment Fund/Foundation	Institute
Characteristics	The association is composed of individuals sharing common interests and objectives. Members come together to pursue their set objectives.	Suitable for a reuse center or reuse point, especially if the organization is primarily engaged in social, scientific, educational, and environmental activities.	Suitable for the operation of a reuse center or reuse point in the case of welfare activities, including projects focused on sustainability and reuse. Carrying out socially or economically beneficial activities.
Legal regulations	Section 214 et seq. of Act No. 89/2012 Sb., the Civil Code	Section 306 et seq. or Section 394 et seq. of Act No. 89/2012 Sb., the Civil Code	Section 402 et seq. of Act No. 89/2012 Sb., the Civil Code
Advantages	A flexible legal form that is used for organizations with a community or social focus.	Independent of short-term fluctuations in finance, it may have its own sources of funding through its assets or investments.	A flexible legal form that is used for organizations with a community or social focus.
Disadvantages	Dependence on funding from membership fees, donations, grants, or other forms. Inability to trade.	It owns and administers its own assets or raises funds, but these must be used only to support specific objectives and projects.	An initial capital deposit or funds to underwrite the activities of the institute must be paid.
Risks	Association members are liable for the association's debts by their property.	Uncertainty and risk if it depends on only one source of funding.	The organization's projects may depend on social and environmental changes.

It is also possible to encounter a charitable trust in practice. This legal person is not listed in the table above because the possibility of establishing a charitable trust was removed with the adoption of Act No. 89/2012 Sb., the Civil Code. Charitable trusts that were established before Act No. 89/2012 Sb., the Civil Code, came into force, i.e., prior to January 1, 2014, could remain in this legal form (Section 3050 of Act No. 89/202 Sb., the Civil Code) or choose to transform into another legal form (foundation, endowment fund, or institute). In the present legal regulations, a charitable trust takes the form of an institute.

If the founder of a reuse center or reuse point needs to set up a business model that integrates social or environmental objectives, the Czech legal system enables them to establish a social enterprise. This form emphasizes achieving social or environmental objectives together with economic sustainability, where the value of a social enterprise is measured not only by financial results but also by social impact. A social enterprise differs from a regular business corporation in its core objectives, attitudes, and the way it creates

values for society. Not every business that identifies itself as a social enterprise is a social enterprise. Social enterprises include businesses that employ disadvantaged people, are environmentally focused, support local development, or engage in fair trade activities. Social enterprise thus combines the economic, social, and environmental dimensions of doing business. Given the nature of the social enterprise's objectives, it can therefore be concluded that it is a hybrid legal form containing elements of a business corporation and non-profit organizations. In the Czech Republic, a social enterprise may select several legal forms for its establishment, which allow for linking business with achieving social or environmental objectives. A social enterprise can take the form of a limited liability company, joint-stock company, cooperative, social cooperative, association, foundation, or self-employed person.

Table 3. Comparing the characteristics of a social enterprise and a social cooperative

Form	Social enterprise	Social cooperative
Characteristics	<p>These are business entities in various legal forms that aim to combine business with achieving social or environmental objectives. The legal forms of a social enterprise can be limited liability company, joint stock company, cooperative, social cooperative, institute, association, foundation, and sole proprietorship.</p> <p>To be defined as a social enterprise, an organization must fulfill public-beneficial objectives that are already defined in the founding documents. Upon its establishment, a social enterprise defines its business activities with an emphasis on social and environmental objectives.</p>	<p>It can be established since 2014. It is based on the principles of social entrepreneurship. It is a cooperative, and in defining its objectives, it can opt for the form of a social enterprise. It consistently carries out activities of public benefit to promote social cohesion.</p> <p>The organization comprises the term "social cooperative."</p>
Legal regulations	<p>The legal regulation of the forms of commercial corporations is Act No. 90/2012 Sb., on Business Corporations and Cooperatives.</p> <p>The legal regulation of non-profit organizations is Act No. 89/2012 Sb., the Civil Code.</p> <p>The legal form of a licensed trade is Act No. 455/1991 Sb., the Trade Licensing Act.</p>	<p>Section 758 of Act No. 90/2012 Sb., on Business Corporations and Cooperatives</p>
Advantages	<p>It is established based on the founders' decision and can be registered under different legal forms— there is a high degree of flexibility.</p> <p>Some entities find it important that a business corporation be mindful of social and environmental responsibility. Better reputation, better attraction of customers and business partners.</p>	<p>A good reputation is an effective tool for business with benefits for society. It is in line with the stated objectives, i.e., creating jobs and supporting the community.</p>
Disadvantages	<p>Fundraising is more difficult.</p> <p>Prioritizing social and environmental objectives can limit profitability.</p> <p>Goals are firmly stated in the founding documents. They cannot be changed or modified.</p>	<p>The objectives are clearly defined in the founding documents. They cannot be changed or modified.</p>
Risks	<p>Business partners may have limited awareness of the concept of social entrepreneurship.</p>	<p>Joint liability of members for the operation and debts of the cooperative.</p>

The term social enterprise is not directly defined by law in the Czech Republic within a single legal norm. The concept of a social enterprise is embedded and intertwined in a number of legal regulations governing the conditions of business activities and social care, or in the Employment Act (Table 3).

The Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs has submitted a bill on social enterprise and amendments to related acts to the Chamber of Deputies. This bill introduces the concept of social economy into the legal system of the Czech Republic and sets out its sub-characteristics. The proposed legal regulation enshrines the means to support registered social enterprises, which should be used to provide comprehensive assistance with the sustainable development of social business activity ("Bill on Social Enterprise").

Establishing a business by a state or local government authority, focusing on municipalities

Under the Czech legal system, only municipalities with an extended scope of authority have the right to establish business corporations (Section 35a of Act No. 128/2000 Sb., Section 14(3) of Act No. 129/2000 Sb.). However, municipalities and regions are limited in establishing business corporations by the fact that the object of the business activities of the established business corporation must be related to the performance of municipal tasks assigned to municipalities in accordance with the relevant legislation. Municipalities may be founders of both legal persons under public law (state-funded organizations) and founders of legal persons and business corporations under private law.

The municipality is entitled to set up a state-funded organization within the meaning of the relevant act (Act No. 218/2000 Sb.). Municipalities and regions can establish state-funded organizations for such activities, which are usually not-for-profit and whose scope and complexity require a separate legal personality. A state-funded organization is therefore a legal person that is established as a state, non-profit organization with a defined public interest. Providing useful services or activities is usually the main objective of a state-funded organization.

Reuse centers and reuse points can also be operated as waste recycling centers (Table 4), especially if the waste recycling center allows for waste separation, repair, or reuse of materials and items. The Czech Republic does not have a specific legal form for waste recycling centers, and their operation can be organized in several ways. Most waste recycling centers are part of the waste management system, and the waste recycling center is operated by the municipality or town, often in cooperation with waste management companies.

3.2. The Identification of Legal Norms Governing the Operation of Reuse Centers, Reuse Points, and their Categorization into Clusters

The operation of reuse centers and reuse points in the Czech Republic is subject to several key legal aspects. For the purposes of this article, the authors list the most important legal regulations (Table 5 and Table 6) that must be complied with in the operation of reuse centers

Table 4. The comparison of the legal forms for the establishment of a reuse facility - a municipality, a city, or a region as a founder

Form	Business corporation	State-funded organization	Waste recycling center	Foundation/endowment fund, association, civic association
Characteristics	Legal limitations for establishing a business corporation must be met; the object of the business corporation must be in accordance with the tasks of the municipality. A municipality may be an owner and may have an ownership interest in a business corporation.	The aim is to provide useful services or activities. It can be established by the municipality, which then finances it. The aim is not to make a profit.	There is no specific legal form in the Czech Republic. Waste recycling centers are part of the waste management system or are operated by municipalities in cooperation with waste management companies, which are established as business corporations.	The conditions set out in Table 2 apply.
Legal regulations	Act No. 90/2012 Sb., on Business Corporations	Act No. 218/2000 Sb., on Budgetary Rules	Act No. 90/2012 Sb., on Business Corporations	Act No. 89/2012 Sb., the Civil Code
Possible legal forms	limited liability company, cooperative, general commercial partnership	State-funded organization	limited liability company, joint stock company	Foundation, endowment fund, association, civic association

and reuse points under the Czech legal system. However, in this context, it needs to be stressed that regarding the business plan and set objectives that precede the establishment of reuse centers and reuse points, they predetermine, to a certain extent, compliance with the relevant legal regulations. In this sense, the legal regulations can be classified as follows:

- the legal regulations that reuse centers and reuse points are required to comply with in their internal operations (tax compliance, bookkeeping, etc.); and
- in its external operations (business relations with third parties, sales, liability for defects, etc.).

4. Discussion and Conclusion

The research questions have been answered based on the defined methods, i.e., the method of interpretation of the relevant legislation at the level of statutes and decrees, the method of analysis of legal regulations and decrees, and the method of comparison of the obtained data. In connection with answering the first research question, two groups of legal persons have been characterized, with emphasis on the entity that establishes the legal person. In the case of operating reuse centers and reuse points as non-profit organizations, one has to take into account the lack of financial resources for the operation of reuse centers and reuse points and a certain degree of financial dependence on third parties. In the case of

Table 5. Synthesizing the legal regulations related to the internal operation of reuse centers and points

Field of law	Issues addressed	Legal norm
Commercial law	- Establishment, entry in the public register	Act No. 89/2012 Sb., the Civil Code Act No. 90/2012 Sb., on Business Corporations and Cooperatives Act No. 304/2013 Sb., on Public Registers
	- Performing administrative duties with respect to the public register (financial statements, audit, etc.) - Keeping a record of the real owners	Act No. 90/2012 Sb., on Business Corporations and Cooperatives Act No. 304/2013 Sb., on Public Registers
Financial law	- Accounting records, records of accounting transactions	Act No. 563/1991 Sb., on Accounting
	- Tax obligations	Act No. 586/1992 Sb., on Income Tax Act No. 235/2004 Sb., on Value Added Tax Act No. 338/1992 Sb., on Real Estate Tax
Civil law	- Lease agreement, contracts relating to internal affairs	Act No. 89/2012 Sb., the Civil Code
Labor law	- Industrial relations, - Relations with self-employed persons	Act No. 262/2006 Sb., the Labor Code Act No. 89/2012 Sb., the Civil Code
Administrative law	- Occupational safety, fire protection, and hygiene	Act No. 309/2006 Sb., Further Requirements on Occupational Health, and Safety Act No. 133/1985 Sb., on Fire Protection Act No. 258/2000 Sb., on Protection of Public Health
	- Waste law, waste sorting and waste management rules. In some cases, it is necessary to obtain a permit for waste collection and sorting. - Registration fees for waste production and management	Act No. 185/2001 Sb., on Waste Act No. 565/1990 Sb., on the Local Fee.
	- Protection of the environment	Act No. 76/2002 Sb., on Integrated Prevention and Reducing Pollution

Table 6. Synthesizing the legal regulations related to the external operation of reuse centers and points

Field of law	Issues addressed	Legal norm
Civil law	- contractual relations with business partners /it also applies to PO/ - contractual relations with third parties - gifts (donations), contributions - warranties for goods - operation of the online shop / it also applies to PO/	Act No. 89/2012 Sb., the Civil Code
	- Consumer protection - Personal data protection	Act No. 89/2012 Sb., the Civil Code Act No. 634/1992 Sb., on Consumer Protection Regulation 2017/2394/EU, on consumer protection Act no. 101/2000 Sb., on Personal Data Protection Regulation 2016/679/EU. General Data Protection Regulation

operating reuse centers and reuse points through a business corporation, the absence of social, environmental, and sustainability elements, which are the main characteristics of reuse centers and reuse points, must be avoided.

The analysis has shown that the present legislation does not sufficiently deal with the existence of legal entities that would incorporate both the element of non-profit activity and the element of business activity in aggregate. Such a form of legal entity would be beneficial for reuse centers and reuse points as it would ensure their potential financial dependence on third parties to a certain extent, whereby reuse centers and reuse points could carry out business activities, and at the same time, the main characteristics of reuse centers and reuse points would be satisfied. While the current legal order provides for the possibility of operating a social cooperative, this legal concept has not yet been sufficiently regulated. The authors appreciate the current initiative of the Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs to submit the Act on Social Enterprise and on Amendments to Related Acts, as the adoption of this Act would contribute to the development of business activities with an implemented social aspect.

Having analyzed the second research question, it has been found that the entity establishing a reuse center or reuse point is crucial for the establishment of the reuse center or reuse point. In the case of a private entity, it is not constrained by the legal order when choosing a legal norm. The opposite situation occurs when the founder is a state authority or a self-governing territorial unit, which is bound by the legal order of the Czech Republic and is thus limited in its choice of the legal form of the reuse center or reuse point.

In the case of identifying the legal sources regulating the operation of reuse centers and points, the basic legal norms and other regulations were defined and clustered into two basic groups: those related to internal operation and those related to external operation. These two basic clusters were further classified by the law types.

The authors positively assess the current initiative of the Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs, which is the proposer of the law on social enterprise and the amendment of related laws. The adoption of this law would contribute to the development of business with an integrated social aspect so that enterprises with a social focus become a natural part of the Czech economy as well (as stated by Tauš Procházková et al., 2021). As Lambooy et al. (2021) point out, many EU member states provide legal forms tailored to social enterprises.

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